

Academic Review on Detection of OCD Links by Gender

Dr. Arzu Ozkan

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Abstract

Although men are more likely to have symptoms throughout childhood, both men and women have an equal chance of being diagnosed with obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD). It is estimated that approximately one quarter of all obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) cases are found in children under the age of 18, and one-third of individuals with OCD have the onset of the disease at a young age. Can a person avoid being OCD? Although the first episode of obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) cannot be prevented, people can learn to control their symptoms after

being diagnosed, according to mental health researchers and experts. People with OCD should keep a diary of their symptoms and find situations or events that may trigger their symptoms. This will allow them to seek immediate treatment if their symptoms worsen. Finding situations or events that may trigger their symptoms can be conducted by keeping a diary. In addition, they must continue to take all their prescriptions exactly as directed. When a patient's symptoms improve or disappear, they may decide to stop taking their medication. However, this is an extremely risky move, as twenty percent of patients stop responding to medications that were previously effective for them because they stop taking the medication as prescribed. How can obsessive compulsive disorder be treated? Medication and talk therapy are common components of OCD treatment plans, and their precise components depend on the patient's unique needs and symptoms. These treatments complement each other to produce an improvement in function and less severe symptoms over time. Medications Antidepressants are the medical term for medications used to treat OCD. Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, or SSRIs, are a type of antidepressant that works by repairing communication malfunctions in the orbitofrontal cortex, caudate nucleus, cingulate gyrus, and basal ganglia.

Keywords: *OCD by Gender, OCD, Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder, How Compulsive Disorder Can Be Treated*

1. Introduction

They do this by increasing the amount of a chemical messenger known as serotonin, which results in an improvement in information processing occurring in various parts of the brain. In most cases, antidepressants can reduce OCD symptoms by 40-60%. Psychotherapy Cognitive behavioral therapy is recognized as one of the most successful treatments for obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) (CBT). The primary goal of cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) is to find and challenge dysfunctional ideas, attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors and then replace them with ones that are more consistent with the individual's goals. Patients receiving CBT are encouraged to face their fears and are helped to change their behavior. In doing so, CBT helps patients cope with their obsessions and resist their compulsions. As a result, patients often see a 60 to 80 percent reduction in their

OCD symptoms . The lifetime prevalence of obsessive-compulsive disorder is 2.32%, but this may be underrepresented as patients often seek care only when their symptoms are moderate to severe. The average age of onset is 19.5 years, and new cases of OCD are exceedingly rare in people in their early 30s.

Early onset symptoms manifest in a subset of patients, predominantly male (before 10 years of age). The lifetime risk of buying obsessive - compulsive disorder (OCD) is generally greater in women who had the disease during their youth. Course of the Disease The effect of OCD on a person's level of functionality and quality of life is significant. It is usually a chronic condition, accounting for sixty to seventy percent of all cases, and prone to relapse if not managed properly. When evidence-based treatments are used, there is a significant chance of improvement and even remission. Patients with a later age of onset, shorter duration of symptoms , strong insight, and good response to first treatment have a higher chance of remission. Early-start and high-intensity treatment for OCD should lead to remission as the goal. Consequently, it is crucial that primary care physicians have the necessary resources to accurately diagnose and treat patients suffering from OCD .

Major challenges in the management of this condition include inadequate treatment options and a lack of resources devoted specifically to OCD . In a study group , only 30.9% of patients with severe symptoms and 2.9% of people with moderately severe symptoms received OCD -specific therapy.

2. pathogenesis

OCD can be divided into three distinct categories: neurobiology, genetics, and environmental factors. It is a mutual exchange. Given the selective response to serotonergic therapy, a disorder in the serotonin system was formerly believed to be the primary cause in the pathophysiology of obsessive -compulsive disorder (OCD). According to more recent research, glutamate, dopamine, and potentially other neurochemicals have also proven to play a role. 8 One scenario presented to

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explain OCD argues that a genetic predisposition to the adverse effects of environmental stresses may lead to changes in the expression of genes involved in neurotransmitter systems.

As a result, both the structure and function of the brain change. 8 Diagnosis Obsessions are patterns of repetitive, unwanted thoughts or ideas that can cause significant emotional distress . The person makes a concerted effort to combat or suppress unwanted thoughts, as they are ego-distorting and are not compatible with the individual's sense of who they are. They can be tainted by contamination, recurring suspicions, or forbidden ideas of a sexual, religious, or unpleasant character. Compulsions are mental or behavioral practices that are repeated over and over to relieve the distress caused by obsessions . People report feeling an overwhelming sense of obligation to perform these actions, which with continued practice eventually become second nature. It can include things like washing hands, checking, ordering, praying, counting, or seeking reassurance.

3. Associated Compulsive Habits

Fear of contagion or infecting others; fear of contamination by germs, diseases or environmental causes; fear of being contaminated by bad or immoral persons ; and fear of contamination by environmental factors, practice of washing or cleaning rituals

recurring ideas that someone is a sexual pedophile or otherwise sexually deviant.

These disorders are often referred to as obsessive -compulsive related disorders. OCD has many different symptoms, some of which are misdiagnosed . OCD is a complex and diverse condition. For example, forbidden thoughts may be attributed to other sources or may not appear to be associated with overt compulsions at first glance . Patients with OCD often engage in mental routines, even if the compulsions are hard to notice. Patients may hesitate to describe their OCD symptoms for a variety of reasons , including feelings of humiliation and stigma, as well as concerns about the possible meanings of their obsessions and the consequences of showing them.

- preoccupations, compulsions, or a combination of the two Obsessions (1) and (2): the presence of an obsession .

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- Recurring thoughts, urges, or pictures that are quite persistent and suddenly met during the disturbance. It's invasive and undesirable and creates a significant amount of anxiety or suffering in most people.

The person tries to ignore or suppress such ideas, impulses, or pictures, or to neutralize them using some other thought or activity (i.e., coercion). (1) and (2) together form the definition of compulsions:

1. *A person feels compelled to undertake repetitive actions (such as washing hands, ordering or checking in) or mental activities (such as complying with regulations that must be followed carefully) because they have to do it.*
2. *Certain behaviors or mental acts are intended to prevent or reduce anxiety or distress, or to prevent some dangerous event or situation; however, such behaviors or mental acts are not realistically linked to or are clearly excessive in relation to what they are designed to neutralize or prevent:*

It is possible that younger teens may not be able to express the rationale behind these mental or behavioral actions. The obsessions or compulsions are time consuming (for example, lasting more than an hour a day) or cause clinically significant distress or impairment in social, work-related, or other critical areas of functioning. Symptoms of obsessive-compulsive disorder are signs of another medical illness or a substance (for example, abuse of a prescription drug cannot be attributed to the physiological effects of a drug). The symptoms of this condition are not better explained by the symptoms of any other mental illness (for example, excessive worry, as in generalized anxiety disorder; preoccupation with appearance, as in body dysmorphic disorder; difficulty getting rid of or detaching from possessions, hair trichotillomania, as in hoarding disorder); Pulling as in hair pulling disorder; skin picking, as in skin picking disorder; stereotypes as in stereotypical movement disorder; ritualized eating behavior as in eating disorders; preoccupation with substances or gambling, as in substance and addiction disorders; illness anxiety, preoccupation with having a disease, as in paraphilic disorders; sexual urges or fantasies, as in paraphilic disorders; impulses as destructive, impulse control and behavioral disorder; and impulses destructive, as impulse control Specify here: With a good or adequate level of insight:

The person with obsessive-compulsive disorder realizes that ideas about the situation are not, or may or may be, certainly or possibly true.

4. Showing a Lack of Insight

The person with obsessive-compulsive disorder is of the opinion that their view is most likely correct. In the absence of awareness and based on delusional beliefs:

The person suffering from obsessive-compulsive disorder is fully convinced that the ideas about the condition are correct. Regularly plucking one's skin reduces or cuts the act of picking, which can lead to skin lesions. 75% of people who suffer from hoarding disorder have a mood or anxiety problem.

5. Trichotillomania (hair pulling disorder) (hair pulling disorder)

A selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor, abbreviated as SSRI. Patients presenting with generalized anxiety or sadness should raise the potential for OCD with treating physicians. Patients can contribute information by referring to recurring thoughts or actions that are considered offensive. It is also unusual for people with anxiety to worry excessively about going to certain places or avoiding certain things, being sick or hurt, and repeatedly seeking reassurance. It is important to keep in mind that obsessive-compulsive personality disorder is a unique diagnostic entity from obsessive -compulsive disorder and is not distinguished by intrusive thoughts or repetitive activities. Instead, it is a common behavioral pattern that emphasizes order, perfectionism, and a sense of control. Obsessive Compulsive Disorder (OCD) is often confused with other diseases. OCD is a common comorbidity for many of these disorders and is potentially important to consider. When the diagnosis is suspected, it is recommended that the patient be referred to a psychiatrist. It is important to investigate whether mental routines or obsessive thoughts affect a person's ability to concentrate and pay attention. It often focuses on practical concerns (like money, health, or loved ones), as opposed to the irrational preoccupations that characterize anxiety, OCD, and autism spectrum disorders. OCD can cause social isolation , but most patients with the disorder

keep their ability to communicate with others; People suffering from OCD often have the feeling that their compulsive repetitive activity is excessive and unreasonable. Depression People suffering from depression are sometimes misdiagnosed with an obsession ; however, the themes of their ruminations are indicative of depression (for example, guilt resulting from inadequacies or negative self-evaluation).

Mental disorder (psychotic) OCD thoughts may also be irrational (for example, fear of catching the human immunodeficiency virus through doorknobs); however, unlike people with psychosis, people with OCD often find that their thoughts are irrational but unable to control them. Psychosis is often characterized by delusional beliefs; OCD thoughts can also be irrational (for example, fear of passing the human immunodeficiency virus through doorknobs).

6. Tourette syndrome

Tourette 's syndrome are usually involuntary; OCD is characterized by a pattern of repetitive activity that comes from a cognitive basis (such as an obsessive need for symmetry) as well as the urge to perform an activity until it is "completely" completed. OCD and ADHD are abbreviations for obsessive -compulsive disorder and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, respectively. Ninety percent of individuals with OCD will also meet the criteria for at least one added mental diagnosis during their lifetime . Anxiety disorders such as panic disorder, social phobia, specific phobias, and post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) are the most common type of mental illness (75.8%). Other often saw conditions include mood disorders (63.3% of patients), most notably major depressive disorder (40.7% of patients), impulse control disorders (55.9% of patients), and drug use disorders. (38.6% of patients). 2 People with OCD are at risk of taking their own life. According to the general population survey, 63% of people with OCD had suicidal ideation and 26% tried to commit suicide.

likelihood of engaging in suicidal behavior increases when a person suffers from a condition such as depression, post- traumatic stress disorder, drug addiction, or an impulse control problem . A smaller group of participants from the main study was randomly selected in many cases to take

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part in an interview via email. To be considered eligible, participants had to be at least 18 years old and had a major diagnosis of OCD. As participants were randomly selected from the database of the larger study, no clear effort was made to recruit people by gender or socioeconomic status. Instead, individuals were selected based on random choice. Recruitment of participants continued until no added information appeared from the interviews or the data saturation point was reached. DSM-IV criteria were used to confirm the main diagnosis of obsessive-compulsive disorder . Face-to-face interviews were conducted with participants who confirmed their interest in taking part in the study by responding to an e-mail invitation. Interviews were conducted in the participants' native language, English, and were led by a semi-structured interview program that included a series of open-ended questions. Participants were asked to answer in their native language. In most cases, the interviews lasted between thirty and sixty minutes. (““Doctor, please tell me it’s nothing serious”: an exploration of ...”) The interviewer (KK) did not interact with the participants before conducting these interviews. The following topics were discussed in depth during the meeting:

- *First memory of OCD symptoms.*
- *daily activity experiences; and*
- *coping methods used over time .*

Before starting the interview, participants completed a demographic questionnaire and the Florida Obsessive-Compulsive Inventory (FOCI) to decide the severity of their OCD symptoms . This was done before the meeting started. Including mild, moderate, severe, and extreme scales as rating categories . In addition, the Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale (Y-BOCS), a scale given by a clinician, was also used to decide the severity of OCD. Scores are further divided into categories such as mild, moderate, severe and extreme. These two measures of severity, FOCI and Y-BOCS, were added to obtain a better picture of the disease profile of the participants. The reliability of qualitative data was ensured by explaining the meaning of participant responses using interpretive strategies.

In the publications that appeared because of this research, the participants were informed that their data would be made completely anonymous and securely stored on the encrypted computers of the students and their advisors. This information was also conveyed to the participants. A travel

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voucher was given to each participant to help cover the costs of traveling to and from the study facility . ATLAS.ti version , a computer-aided qualitative data analysis program, was used to perform theme analysis (TA) on the transcripts . Analysis of the transcripts followed a six-step data analysis approach that included the following steps:

- (1) familiarity with the data.*
- (2) data and generating a first code list.*
- (3) codes and creation of themes.*
- (4) Reviewing each theme created in Step 3.*
- (5) refining, defining and assigning descriptive tags to each theme; and*
- (6) data analysis results*

Trying to fix them would be a complete waste of time. At the end of the worrying phase, you need to take some time to collect yourself, try to avoid thinking about anything but the problem at hand, and only then return to your typical routines. It is important to schedule activities unrelated to fixation at other times of the day. You should jot down any ideas that come to mind as you go through the day's events so you can "postpone" them until you have more time to think about them. Putting an end to your thoughts can be conducted by evaluating them. Asking yourself these questions during the anxious phase can help you overcome any unpleasant or intrusive ideas that may preoccupy your mind. How does the evidence support this idea, and how exactly does it do that?

Epidemics have had a significant impact on human society throughout human history. They manage the deaths of millions, economic depressions, and in some cases the collapse of entire empires.

The term "pandemic" is used to describe a disease that is difficult to control and affects large numbers of people all over the world. The word "epidemic" is used to describe a disease that affects an alarmingly high number of people in a particular area or region. Pandemics have the potential to have a long-term impact not only on people's mental health, but also on their culture, government and religion for decades to come. Over the past few decades, research on pandemics has shown that large numbers of individuals have both short-term and long-term detrimental

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effects on their psychological health. This applies both at once after the pandemic and for the long-term effects. The SARS-CoV-2 virus was the cause of the pandemic, also called Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). It started in December 2019 in Wuhan, China and quickly spread throughout China. (“Effects of COVID-19 Pandemic on Depressive Symptoms among Poor Urban ...”) This pandemic managed the increase in the death rate seen all over the world. As of February 16, 2022, there were more than 414 million documented cases of virus infection worldwide, and more than 5.8 million deaths can be directly attributed to the viral disease and its repercussions.

Therefore, changes occur not only in the structure of the brain, but also in its function. Diagnosis Obsessions are recurring, unwanted thought patterns that can cause significant mental distress if not addressed. Because unwanted ideas corrupt the ego and do not match the individual's feeling of who they are, the person makes an intense effort to resist or suppress them. They may be contaminated by contamination, repeated suspicions, or forbidden concepts of a sexual, religious, or objectionable nature. People say they experience an overwhelming sense of duty to perform these actions that, with continued practice, eventually become second nature. Washing hands, checking, ordering, praying, counting, or seeking reassurance may all fall under this category.

- *Don't be afraid to be around others and avoid other people and their company.*
- *Recurring thoughts that the person is a sexual pedophile or otherwise sexually deviant.*
- *Recurring thoughts of behaving sexually inappropriately towards other people.*

In addition, it is now classified along with several other disorders with similar characteristics to OCD. These conditions are often referred to as obsessive-compulsive spectrum disorders. OCD is a disease that can take many forms, some of which are misdiagnosed. This makes it a disease that is both complex and difficult to diagnose. For example, prohibited ideas may be attributed to other sources or may not appear at first glance to be due to obvious coercion. Another possibility is that the person may not even be aware that they have these thoughts. Patients suffering from OCD often engage in mental routines, even if the compulsions are hard to see. Patients may be reluctant to show their OCD symptoms for a variety of reasons, including feelings of shame and stigma, as well as concern about the possible meanings of their obsessions and the consequences of showing them. Patients may also be concerned about the potential benefits of showing their

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symptoms . Ideas, impulses, or images that resurface repeatedly; they are very stubborn; and they are met suddenly when deterioration occurs. The individual tries to ignore or suppress such thoughts, desires, or images, or neutralize them by using another thought or some type of action (i.e., by coercion). Taken together, the following items form the definition of compulsions:

1. *Behaviors that a person feels compelled to do (such as washing their hands, ordering, or checking in) or mental activities (such as following carefully enforced regulations) as a response because they must. Hand washing, ordering or checking are examples of compulsions.*
2. *Certain behaviors or mental acts are performed to prevent or reduce anxiety or distress, or to prevent some dangerous event or situation; however, such behaviors or mental acts are not realistically linked to or are clearly excessive in relation to what they are designed to neutralize or prevent:*

Young children are likely to be unable to express the underlying logic of these mental or behavioral ones. The obsessions or compulsions take a significant amount of time (for example, last more than an hour a day) or cause clinically significant distress or impairment in social, work-related, or other key areas of functioning. The signs and symptoms of obsessive-compulsive disorder are indeed indicators of another medical condition, or a substance use problem (for example, abuse cannot be attributed to the physiological effects of a prescription drug, a drug). The symptoms of this condition are not better explained by the symptoms of any other mental illness (for example, excessive worry, as in generalized anxiety disorder; preoccupation with appearance, as in body dysmorphic disorder; difficulty getting rid of or separation from what they have, hair trichotillomania , as in hoarding disorder); pulling as in hair pulling disorder; skin picking, as in skin picking disorder; stereotypes as in stereotypical movement disorder; As with the hair, Please indicate below: If the individual with obsessive compulsive disorder has an acceptable or excellent level of insight and, as a result, is aware that the concepts associated with the illness are either absolutely or absolutely inaccurate.

7. Demonstrating a Lack of Understanding

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believes that their perspective is in the right place . Preoccupation with perceived defects in one's physical appearance or with actual deficiencies in one's physical appearance leads to repetition of actions or ideas in response to overt concerns about one's appearance. The first sign of symptoms usually appears at the onset of puberty. The area used to stack items can no longer be used as intended. People suffering from hoarding disorder are more likely than the general population to have problems with their mood or anxiety. The hoarding-related behaviors that people engage in are getting increasingly violent. Behavior modification to reduce new product intake and get rid of buildup over time Insufficient evidence to support drug use.

Obsessive Compulsive Disorder, often known as OCD, is often confused with other disorders. It is important to consider the possibility of having more than one diagnosis, especially since OCD is a common comorbidity associated with many of these conditions. If the diagnosis is uncertain, referral to a psychiatrist is strongly recommended. Adolescent ADHD sufferers People with ADHD often procrastinate and have trouble focusing their attention and paying attention to details. People with OCD feel the need to achieve everything "totally" or "totally" and may therefore appear to have ADHD because they cannot finish what they have started; It is extremely important to analyze whether a person's mental habits or obsessive thoughts affect their ability to focus and pay attention.

Unlike the irrational preoccupations that are characteristic of OCD and autism spectrum disorders, the concerns underlying anxiety are often grounded in the real world (such as a person's finances, health, or loved ones). People suffering from OCD often have the idea that the compulsive repetitive activity they engage in is excessive and unreasonable. Although OCD can cause social isolation , most patients with this condition keep their ability to interact with others. People struggling with depression can sometimes misunderstand their condition as an obsession, even though the subjects of their rumination are characteristic of depression (for example, guilt stemming from inadequacies or negative self-evaluation). People with obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) may also have irrational thoughts (for example, fear of catching the human immunodeficiency virus from doorknobs); however, unlike people with psychosis, people with OCD often know that their thoughts are irrational but cannot control them. Beliefs that are irrational or delusional are a common feature of psychosis. Tourette syndrome OCD is

characterized by a repetitive pattern of behavior that comes from a cognitive basis (such as an obsessive need for symmetry) as well as the urge to perform an activity until it is "completely" completed. Tourette syndrome is characterized by involuntary physical or verbal tics, while OCD is characterized by the urge to perform an activity until it is "completely" completed. The terms obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) can be abbreviated as OCD and ADHD, respectively.

8. Clinical Practice

OCD will also meet criteria for at least one other mental disorder in their lifetime. This is true even if they do not currently meet the requirements for this diagnosis. The most common type of mental illness that co-occurs are anxiety disorders, which can take the form of panic disorder, social phobia, specific phobias, and post- traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). This category accounts for 75.8% of all comorbid mental illnesses. Mood disorders (63.3% of patients), particularly major depressive disorder (40.7% of patients), impulse control disorders (55.9% of patients), and substance use disorders are among other common diseases that are often seen. (38.6% of patients). Mood disorders are 63.3% of patients. OCD patients are much more likely to end their own lives by killing their own lives. According to a study of the general population, 63% of people suffering from OCD admitted to having suicidal thoughts at some point in their lives, and 26% tried to take their own life. When a person suffers from a condition such as depression, post- traumatic stress disorder, drug addiction, or trouble with impulse control, they are more likely to engage in behaviors that may lead to suicide, the following topics have been explored in detail:

- (1) *Earliest recall of OCD symptoms.*
- (2) *daily activities; and*
- (3) *coping mechanisms used over time .*

Before starting the interview, it is important to perform a demographic survey for each participant, as well as the Florida Obsessive-Compulsive Inventory (FOCI), which is used to measure participants' OCD symptoms and decide their severity level.

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In the papers that appeared from this study, the participants were assured that their data would be completely anonymized, securely stored on the computers of the students and their advisors, and that this information would be kept encrypted. The computer-aided qualitative data analysis program ATLAS.ti version 7 was used to perform theme analysis (TA) on the transcripts:

- (1) Getting acquainted with data.*
- (2) Coding Related Citations of Data and Creating Initial Code List.*
- (3) Improvement of Codes and Creation of Themes.*
- (4) In Step 3, Examining Each Theme Created.*
- (5) Developing, Defining and Assigning Descriptive Tags to Each Theme; and*

At the end of the worrying phase, you need to take some time to collect yourself, try to avoid thinking about anything but the problem at hand, and only then return to your typical routines. It is important to schedule activities unrelated to fixation at other times of the day. You should jot down any ideas that come to mind as you go through the day's events so you can "postpone" them until you have more time to think about them. Putting an end to your thoughts can be conducted by evaluating them. Asking yourself these questions during the anxious phase can help you overcome any unpleasant or intrusive ideas that may preoccupy your mind.

9. Conclusion

If you have obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD), you should note and write down any unpleasant thoughts or obsessions. This is because your brain will get used to it and will no longer be frightened by it. If you make a considerable effort to deal with your worries or obsessions on a regular basis, you may find that you worry less and less over time. This can be the case if you put in the effort. After this point you will have the opportunity to take part in the event once again, but this time with a new profession. Epidemics have had a significant impact on human society throughout human history . Severe anxiety disorder, known as obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), is characterized by obsessions and compulsions that are difficult to control. Obsessive thoughts can cause a person to engage in behaviors known as compulsions, which are activities

that the individual feels compelled to do. One definition of an obsession is an unwanted concept that constantly pops up in a person's mind and causes the person to feel distressed. OCD is a disorder that has a high degree of individuality and can manifest itself in a wide variety of ways. In the past, these sensations were only seen in OCD patients after meeting anything believed to be contaminated. As a result, concerns have been raised about methods that could be used to distinguish between obsessive-compulsive worries and behaviors unique to people suffering from OCD and reasonable fears and behaviors exhibited during COVID-19, Aardema et al. (12), one of the aspects that distinguishes the two groups from each other is the psychological connotation associated with the term "infection".

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